

HANDELIA TRICHOPHYLLA POLYSACCHARIDES

Sh. O. Ashirbaeva^{1,2}F. A. Kodiralieva²R. K. Rakhmanberdyeva²¹Branch of the Russian Chemical-Technological University named after D. I. Mendeleev,
Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan²S.Yu. Yunusov Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances., Tashkent city, Republic of
Uzbekistan

e-mail: fatimahon.82@mail.ru

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Relevance: *Handelia trichophylla* is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Asteraceae family, widespread in Central Asia. The plant contains a rich complex of biologically active substances: essential oils, sesquiterpene lactones, flavonoids, polysaccharides, tannins, amino acids, choline, carotenoids, ascorbic acid, organic acids, and sugars. Studying the carbohydrate complex of this species is of interest for the search for new sources of natural polysaccharides with potential biological activity.

Study Objective: Isolation and characterization of the carbohydrate complex (alcohol-soluble sugars, water-soluble polysaccharides, pectin substances, and hemicelluloses) from the flowers, leaves, and stems of *H. trichophylla*.

Materials and Methods: The study subject was air-dried, ground raw materials (flowers, leaves, and stems) of *H. trichophylla*.

1. The raw materials were pre-treated with a mixture of chloroform and methanol to remove fatty acids. 2. Extraction was performed with boiling 82% ethanol; alcohol-soluble sugars (ASS), identified by biochemical analysis as fructose and sucrose, were isolated. 3. Water-soluble polysaccharides (WSPS), pectin substances (PS), and hemicelluloses (HMC) were isolated from the residue. 4. Monosaccharide composition was determined by HPLC (Table 1).

Table 1. Content and monosaccharide composition of polysaccharides

Type PS	Yield, %	Monosaccharide Composition, HPLC in %					UAc, PC
		<i>Rha</i>	<i>Ara</i>	<i>Xyl</i>	<i>Glc</i>	<i>Gal</i>	
Flowers							
WSPS	3.76	-	61.9	19.78	12.1	6.2	+
PS	2.32	30.2	7.69	31.2	24.1	6.7	+
HMS	1.24	54.7	51.6	31.6	2.61	5.4	+
Leaves							
WSPS	5.0	10.1	47.8	15.5	9.26	17.2	+
PS	7.0	-	44.87	27.96	15.16	12.0	+
HMS	9.8	61.07	30.3	-	6.35	2.27	+
Stems							
WSPS	0.6	49.75	35.85	-	7.46	6.93	+
PS	2.2	-	40.32	33.31	15.09	11.26	+
HMS	7.4	86.5	10.9	-	0.58	1.98	+

The highest content of WPPS, PV, and HMC was found in *H. trichophylla* leaves. All isolated polysaccharides were acidic in nature; neutral sugars were present in varying proportions, but xylose was the dominant monosaccharide. Fructose and sucrose were detected in the alcohol-soluble fraction.